

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF JOB SATISFACTION AND POSITIVE THINKING AMONG THE PUBLIC AND PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES: A CASE OF CAPITAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

The present study focus on Positive thinking and job satisfaction among university faculty in public and private universities in Islamabad, Pakistan. The purpose of the study is to see if faculty members' levels of job satisfaction are significantly affected by positive thinking. Regression analysis was used to conduct a quantitative analysis of survey data from 447 faculty participants. Pay, promotion, rewards, supervision, coworker relationships, benefits, operating conditions, nature of work, and communication were all used to assess job satisfaction, and a validated scale focusing on optimism and pessimism was used to assess positive thinking. Positive thinking is positively correlated with overall job satisfaction ($F = 41.319$, $p = .000$), according to the findings. The rejection of the null hypothesis that there is no significant association between positive thinking and job satisfaction is supported by the fact that positive thinking explains between 1.6% and 12.5% of variance across various dimensions of job satisfaction. Pay, promotion, rewards, supervision, coworker relationships, benefits, operating conditions, the nature of work, and communication were all found to be influenced by positive thinking. The implications of these findings suggest that encouraging faculty members to think positively could increase job satisfaction. Workshops on positive psychology, training in positive thinking strategies, and the promotion of a positive work environment through incentives and recognition are all suggestions. The longitudinal effects of positive thinking interventions on job satisfaction and productivity in academic settings could be the focus of future research.

INTRODUCTION

This study aims to explore what has been done in the area of positive thinking with regard to job satisfaction. There are two constructs in this study.

Firstly, the positive thinking related to job activities and secondly job satisfaction. Positive thinking is viewed as thinking process which leads to desirable

consequences. In other words, optimism refers to positive thought generation that gives life to hopes and dreams and make goals achievable, having positive impact on physical and mental health.

Positive mental state benefits by enabling one to handle daily matters more appropriately. Positive thinking relieves agitation and eliminates toxic negative thoughts from mind. Positive attitude towards life is a healthy lifestyle, it will bring about productive changes in life and is a source of happiness, hope and success.

Optimistic outlook gives whole new perspective to things and brings happiness and success within reach. When you shift your focus on positive aspect of the things, you

Will begin to appreciate the miracles of life and be contented for so many blessings. This positive attitude eventually spreads out and influences everyone around.

Second construct of this research is job satisfaction. It refers to how one regards his professional life. The individual may have positive or negative mood or feeling towards their work. Job satisfaction can be evaluated by workers attitude and inclination to their job. If an employee is contented with his work he will put his all effort and be pleased with the outcome however, if someone is uncomfortable there will be negative feelings. Satisfaction of someone at his place of work can be judged by their quality of work. . The variables of job satisfaction are presented by the famous theories of Hertzberg, Maslow, Aldever, Locke and others. It has nine dimensions or aspects: namely pay, promotion, rewards, supervision, coworker, benefits, operating condition, nature of work, communication.

Ever since 1930, there has been a lot of concern about how the well-being of employees affect their proficiency and satisfaction. Hersey (1932) suggested significant association between employee's attitude and their output, whereas according to Kornhauser (1932) the productivity of workers is not influenced at all by their beliefs and demeanor. It is imperative for the sake of progress and betterment of an organization, to understand link between worker's satisfaction, wellbeing and their productivity. According to Wright 2004, It is still matter of debate in spite of all the study done on the subject, that happiness at workplace tends to improve

performance or not. Researchers claim that disparity in research findings on relation between job satisfaction and effective performance is due to incongruous assessment. In the studies done on interconnection of happiness with productive performance at workplace, happiness is viewed as determinant of job satisfaction (Brief 2002) but it may not be a valid substitute.

Statement of Problem

It is said that the Positive thinkers remain satisfied with their work while negative thinkers perceive the adversarial situations and remain displeased with their jobs. This study is conducted to compare the positive thinking and level of job satisfaction among teachers at public and private sector universities in Islamabad.

Objectives of Study

To find out the relationship between positive thinking and job satisfaction level among faculty members in public and private universities of Islamabad.

Research Question

What is the level of relationship between job satisfaction and positive thinking among faculty members of public and private sector universities of Islamabad?

Hypotheses of the study

H0: There is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and Job satisfaction level of faculty members in public and private sector universities of Islamabad.

Significance of the study

A Positive Attitude induces joy and brightens outlook towards successful living. It helps to deal with daily matters and stressors of life efficiently. Optimism in life safeguards against effects of negative thinking. This research aims to assist teachers to develop positive thinking and attitude to provide scaffolding for their students. This is a laborious task and positive thinking will keep them contented and motivated. Otherwise negative thinking causes one be disquieted with the work and make it difficult to carry on.

This study will benefit the Organizers and policy makers of Education system in creating comfortable and confident work environment for university teachers, increasing their sense of job satisfaction. Positive thinking has important ramifications as regard all aspects of health. Apart from improving health, it benefits students in their personal growth and education process. Positive thinking discourages negative thought process which defers student's full potential.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Positive thinking can be observed as the happier side of the circumstances. As indicated by Jorden, (2006) that it is consciously effort to deal with one's own opinions, speech, emotions, beliefs, and nonverbal behaviors, will only lead to good results, not the possibility of adverse consequences in any difficult, hard or challenging situation.

As indicated by Fredrickson (1998), positive sentiments energize meditation and innovativeness and result in building of social, academic and physical belonging. In an Australian study, positive thinking has been described in term of individual's attributes, for example, hope, acceptance, battling spirits and good faith and participators dealing effectively with ailment (O, Baugh, 2003). As per McGrath, (2006) It is related with an assortment of things like, hopefulness, optimism and confidence.

A positive thinker is energetic and expects satisfaction, joy and a positive result of each incident and act. It makes a man profitable and inventive by considering genuine solution for the issues dispassionately and rationally. It is a mental approach that needs valuable and productive contemplations, words and descriptions that guarantee improvement and success. It is a mental demeanor that may give advantages to patients in term of enabling them to adapt to illness (Schou, 2005).

While negative thinking is the inability to comprehend and observe the positive qualities of an affair. The way we observe things provides the basis for either self-demoralization or criticism (Teasdale, 1978). Such type of thinking helps to overcome many issues possessed by a depressed individual such as, low self-esteem, frustration and anxiety (Peden, 2000) and maintain the dispirited temperament

(Seligman, 1978). People having pessimistic thinking foresee the worse most of the time. They become dysfunctional in managing and handling the matters so they are more inclined to physical and psychological disorders.

According to McGrath, (2006), the characteristics of positive thinking are confidence, hope, optimism, positive affect, well-being etc. Carr (2004) stated that positive thinking is the development of well-being and it is used in the scientific study for developing positive social system and enhancing personal strengths for the advancement of ideal well-being. The views of McGrath (2004) about positive thinking include the reflection of the actions, behavior, attitudes and beliefs of an individual.

According to Wilkinson (2000) positive thinking is an idiom having the characteristics of generality and vagueness. The idea of positive psychology is not a new term in our Pakistani culture. For the internal satisfaction of an individual he adopts different qualities such as tolerance, honesty, dealing with hardship and wisdom which we learn through our religion.

Wilkinson (2000) presented the idea that positive thinking is just like an idiom that has ambiguities and some generalities as well. While the critics say that the ideas of optimistic and positive thinking along with the concept of good life are transferable to other culture with different norms customs and even languages, without much misunderstanding and risk.

Different people define the concept of job satisfaction in different ways. Still there is no single agreement regarding the definition of job satisfaction. So different authors/people define job satisfaction in different way.

According to Anderson (2001), job satisfaction is positive or pleasurable emotional state of an individual which is the result of his/her job experience. It can also be the result of appraisal from the job. This definition has covered both cognition and affective effects. Appraisal refers to the cognition while affective refers to the emotional state. This job satisfaction is a result of cognition (thinking) and affect (feelings)

Definition of Robbins (2005) also conforms the idea of Anderson (2001). According to him, job satisfaction is "feelings of an individual towards the

job". These feelings can be positive or negative. A satisfied person definitely has positive feelings towards job while dissatisfied person definitely has negative feelings towards job. So, job satisfaction is overall reaction of an individual towards his/her job. Job satisfaction can be described as discrepancy between individual's expectations and actual outcomes.

According to Hewstone (2001) job satisfaction is the reaction of an individual towards the job that is the result of comparison between actual and desired outcomes. Thus performance is linked with individual's expectations regarding the reward and needs fulfillment so employee's satisfaction and performance is dependent on the fulfillment of needs.

According to Saiyadain (2007), job satisfaction refers to the feelings which a person experiences after the accomplishment of task. Positive or negative feelings depend on the outcomes of the task. The intensity of feelings either job satisfaction or dissatisfaction also differ.

Job satisfaction or dissatisfaction is also associated with other factors like nature of work, pay, coworkers, supervisors, and subordinates (George, 2008). Darboe (2003) views job satisfaction as employee's positive feelings for their job as well as for their job environment.

Foragher and Copper (2005) describe the job satisfaction as an emotional reaction and positive attitude which individual possess about their job and environment. Simatwa (2011) also relates the job satisfaction with the performance.

Employees with high level of job satisfaction perform better (Scott, 2004). According to Schmid (2007) individual's attractiveness towards his/her job is a result of positive or negative consequences which individual face at workplace. According to Okpara (2006), it is an effective reaction of an individual towards his/her job, which is the result of comparison between actual outcomes and desired outcomes.

Job satisfaction can also be described as an employee's sense of success and achievement on the job. It has a link with the organizational productive and wellbeing as satisfied employees enjoy their work and put their maximum effort to do the work well. Job satisfaction leads to promotion, recognition,

income, and goals achievement (Kaliski 2007). Job satisfaction is also associated with the rewards in form of intrinsic motivation (Statt, 2004). Job satisfaction has three components: Cognitive, emotional and behavioral. Cognitive aspect of an individual for his/her of job satisfaction demand the mentally challenging and demanding work. Whereas, emotional side of an individual for their job satisfaction demands the excitement, satisfaction and reward.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research study was conducted to compare the positive thinking and satisfaction in job by members of faculty in public and private sector universities. This chapter reveals the details of the nature of study, methods of research, design of study, population of the research, sampling technique, size of sample, tools of research, etc.

Design of the study

The research was a comparative and descriptive study by design. Quantitative research approach was used to test the hypotheses. For analysis of data gathered, quantitative research approach was used. According to nature of this study, quantitative methods are used to explore the positive thinking and job satisfaction of university teachers. Using quantitative research approach theories are tested. Relationship is found between variables by using inventories, and statistical procedures are applied for analysis. (Creswell, 2014).

Two variables were used in this study. Positive thinking was used as an independent variable of research, and job satisfaction and its nine dimensions were used as reliant variable. Survey design method was selected to collect the views of the representative samples from the population. Survey design was selected due to the economic characteristics of the survey design which are part of the data collection. The questionnaire was used for collection of data. It gives the opportunity to gather numerical portrayal of opinions of chosen sample, so the information collected from the sample can be used for the population s generalization. (Fowler, 2009 and Creswell, 2014). Two questionnaires were disseminated in paper form to teachers in public

and private universities in Islamabad. Personal contacts were used for gathering the information.

Variables of Research

Positive thinking

Positive thinking is described as a mental attitude of an individual in which individual expects favorable and good results. In the process of positive thinking individual creates thoughts and transforms thoughts in to reality. A mind with positivity waits for health, happy ending and happiness in any situation.

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction alludes to the views of the person towards his work. It can be positive or negative considerations towards the work the person does. It can be measured by the satisfaction of staff or worker. If the employee is satisfied with incentives

which he gets at the end of the job, then a positive feeling will arise but if employee is not satisfied or happy with his incentives and rewards then a negative feeling will arise. Satisfaction reflects the worker's input.

Population of the study

The research population was all the teachers of the both strata (public and private universities) in Islamabad. There were 14 universities from public sector and 4 universities from private sector up to 2015 in Islamabad. Total faculty was 7294 in numbers.6119 faculty members were in public sector universities and 1175 faculty members were in private sector universities.

Total Faculty of Islamabad Universities public and private sectors

Sr. No.	Year	Province	Public	Private	Total Full Time Faculty
1	2014-15	Islamabad	6119	1175	7294

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

Sampling Technique

Sampling techniques involve selecting a sub set of participants from the statistical population to estimate the characteristics of the whole population. Descriptive comparative studies had shown that convince or opportunity sampling techniques should be used to determine the results of the population. Since this study involves the comparison between public and private sectors, opportunity sampling is the most appropriate technique.

International Islamic university, NUML, Quaid e Azam University and COMSATS were taken from public sector and Preston University, CUST, Mohi-ud-Din Islamic University and Iqra University were taken from private sector. Faculty from international Islamic university was 72 with 16.1 percentage. 47 with 10.5 percentage were taken from NUML, 66 with 14.8 percentages were taken from Quaid e Azam and 81 with 18.1 percentage were taken from COMSATS. From private sector the faculty taken from Preston University was 42 with 9.4 percentage. The faculty of CUST was 51 with 11.4 percentage, 18 with 4.0 percent were taken from Mohi-ud-Din Islamic university and from Iqra University 70 with 15.7 percent were taken. Opportunity sampling technique was used for the selection of sample size due to appropriateness of procedure and availability of faculty members in universities.

Sample Size

Four hundred and forty-seven teachers of universities were taken from two strata (public and private sectors universities) of Islamabad. Four universities were taken from public sector and four universities were taken from private sector.

Table 3.2 Sample size of the study

Sector	Universities	N	Percentage	Sub Total
Public	International Islamic university	72	16.1	266
	NUML	47	10.5	
	Quid-e-Azam university	66	14.8	
	COMSATS	81	18.1	
Private	Preston university	42	9.4	181
	CUST	51	11.4	
	Mohi-ud-Din Islamic University	18	4.0	

Iqra university	70	15.7
	Total	447

Instrument

Two instruments were used for measuring positive thinking and job satisfaction. For measuring the positive thinking of the subjects in work place the Positive Thinking inventory was used which was developed by Carver, in 2013. For measuring job satisfaction of universities’ faculty, questionnaire developed by Paul (1994) having nine dimensions was used.

Five-point scale used for positive thinking

- 1. Strongly disagree
- 2. Disagree
- 3. Neutral
- 4. Agree
- 5. Strongly agree

Instrument for measuring positive thinking

For measuring the positive thinking of university faculty, Positive thinking inventory, developed by carver (1985, 1994, and 2013) was used. For scoring procedures adopted inventory was used. There were ten questions. The five-point scale was used to collect information about these two continuum.

Coding procedure used for positive thinking

Majority statements in instrument, were used for the 1 strongly disagree, 2 was used for disagree, 3 was used for the neutral, 4 was used for agree and 5 was used for strongly agree. In some statements reverse coding was used which were 3, 7, and 9 and some items are fillers. They are not included in scoring Filler items are 2, 5, 6, and 8. Details of instrument scoring is as follows.

Description of positive thinking inventory with item numbers.

Variables	Total no of items	Question items
Optimism	3	1, 4, 10
Pessimism	3	3,7,9
Filler items	4	2,5,6,8

Instrument used for Determining Job satisfaction

Second construct of research is job satisfaction. Questionnaire, developed by Paul, 1994 was used for measuring the job satisfaction. In this framework nine dimensions were used which are pay, supervision, promotion, operating condition, rewards, benefits, co-worker, nature of work and communication. Each dimension contains four questions so there are total thirty-six questions.

Six-point scale used for job satisfaction

- 1 = Disagree very much
- 2 = Disagree moderately
- 3 = Disagree slightly
- 4 = Agree slightly
- 5 = Agree moderately
- 6 = Agree very much

Coding procedure

Reverse code items are 2, 4, 6, 8, 10,12,14,16,18,19,21,23,24,26,29,31,34 and 36

Description of job satisfaction scale with item numbers

Subscale	Item numbers
Pay	1, 10, 19, 28
Promotion	2, 11, 20, 33
Supervision	3, 12, 21, 30
Fringe Benefits	4, 13, 22, 29
Contingent rewards	5, 14, 23, 32

Operating conditions	6, 15, 24, 31
Coworkers	7, 16, 25, 34
Nature of work	8, 17, 27, 35
Communication	9, 18, 26, 36
Total satisfaction	1-36

ANALYSIS OF DATA

Data analysis was made with the help of SPSS 21. For the achievement of objectives and hypotheses

analysis mean, t-test, frequency, ANOVA and Regression were used.

Objective, hypotheses and statistical procedures

Objectives	Hypotheses	Statistical procedure used
Objective To find out the relationship of positive thinking and job satisfaction level of faculty members in public and private universities of Islamabad.	There is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job satisfaction of faculty members in public and private sector universities of Islamabad.	regression

Ethical Consideration

In procedure of research, moral consideration was also taken into account. This study was an attempt to compare the positive thinking and job satisfaction of university teachers of Islamabad. Names of the respondent were kept confidential. Participants participated willingly.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULT INTERPRETATION

Data analysis regarding relationship of positive thinking and job satisfaction of university faculty in both sectors.

HO1 There is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job Satisfaction level of faculty members in public and private sector universities of Islamabad.

Relationship of positive thinking and job satisfaction

Predictors	B	t	R Square	F	Sig
Positive thinking	.235	6.428	.085	41.319	.000

*p<.05,

The results of above table indicate that the F-value 41.319 is significant as p=.000. The value of coefficient B is .235. So, significant and positive relationship between positive thinking and job

satisfaction is present. Results also explain that positive thinking is bringing 8.5% variation in the job satisfaction of university faculty in both sectors. It rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job satisfaction.

Relationship of positive thinking and pay dimension of job satisfaction

Predictors	B	t	R Square	F	Sig
Positive thinking	.262	5.092	.055	25.927	.000

* $p < .05$,
The results of table show that the F-value is 25.927 which reveals that it is significant as $p = .000$. The value of coefficient B is .262. So, significant and positive relationship between positive thinking and pay sub variable of job satisfaction is present. Result

also explains that positive thinking is bringing 5.5% variation in the job satisfaction of university faculty in both sectors. This rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job satisfaction.

Relationship of positive thinking and promotion dimension of job satisfaction

Predictors	B	t	R Square	F	Sig
Positive thinking	.169	3.376	.025	11.400	.001

* $p < .05$
The results of above table show that the F-value is 11.400 which reveals that it is significant as $p = .001$. The value of coefficient B is .169. So, significant and positive relationship between positive thinking and

promotion sub variable of job satisfaction is present. Results also explain that positive thinking is bringing 2.5% variation in the job satisfaction of university faculty in both sectors. The null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job satisfaction is rejected.

Relationship of positive thinking and Rewards dimension of positive thinking

Predictors	B	t	R Square	F	Sig
Positive thinking	.255	4.951	.052	24.513	.000

* $p < .05$
The values of above table indicate that the F-value is 24.513 which is significant as $p = .000$. The value of coefficient B is .255. So, significant and positive relationship between positive thinking and rewards sub variable of job satisfaction is present. Results

also explain that positive thinking is bringing 5.2 % variation in the job satisfaction of university faculty in both sectors rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job satisfaction.

Relationship of positive thinking and supervision dimension of job satisfaction

Predictors	B	t	R Square	F	Sig
Positive thinking	.179	4.157	.037	17.277	.000

* $p < .05$
The results of table 4.11 explain that the F-value is 17.277 which reveals that it is significant as $p = .000$. The value of coefficient B is .179. So, significant and positive relationship between positive thinking and

supervision sub variable of job satisfaction is present. Results also explain that positive thinking is bringing 3.7 % variation in the job satisfaction of university faculty in both sectors rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job satisfaction.

Relationship of positive thinking and coworker dimension of job satisfaction

Predictors	B	t	R Square	F	Sig
Positive thinking	.246	5.288	.059	27.958	.000

*p<.05

The values of table 4.12 show that the F-value is 27.958 which reveals that it is significant as p=.000. The value of coefficient B is .246. So, significant and positive relationship between positive thinking and coworker sub variable of job satisfaction is present.

Results also explain that positive thinking is bringing 5.9 % variation in the job satisfaction of university faculty in both sectors rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job satisfaction

Relationship of positive thinking and Benefits dimension of job satisfaction

Predictors	B	t	R Square	F	Sig
Positive thinking	.181	3.496	.027	12.223	.001

*p<.05

The results of above table indicate that the F-value is 12.223 which reveals that it is significant as p=.001. The value of coefficient B is .181. So, significant and positive relationship between positive thinking and benefits sub variable of job satisfaction is present.

Results also explain that positive thinking is bringing 2.7 % variation in the job satisfaction of university faculty in both sectors thus rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job satisfaction.

Relationship of positive thinking and operating conditions dimension of job satisfaction

Predictors	B	t	R Square	F	Sig
Positive thinking	.139	2.681	.016	7.190	.008

*p<.05

The results of table 4.14 shows that the F-value is 7.190 which reveals that it is significant as p=.008. The value of coefficient B is .139. So, significant and positive relationship between positive thinking and operating conditions sub variable of job satisfaction is present. Results also explain that positive thinking

is bringing 1.6 % variation in the job satisfaction of university faculty in both sectors thus rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job satisfaction.

Relationship of positive thinking and nature of work dimension of job satisfaction

Predictors	B	t	R Square	F	sig
Positive thinking	.268	5.022	.054	25.220	.000

*p<.05

The values of table explain that the F-value is 25.220 which reveals that it is significant as p=.000. The value of coefficient B is .268. So, significant and positive relationship between positive thinking and nature of work sub variable of job satisfaction is present. Results also explain that positive thinking is

bringing 5.4 % variation in the job satisfaction of university faculty in both sectors thus rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job satisfaction.

Relationship of positive thinking and communication dimension of job satisfaction

Predictors	B	t	R Square	F	Sig
Positive thinking	.420	7.989	.125	63.825	.000

*p<.05

The values of table indicate that the F-value is 63.825 which reveals that it is significant as p=.000. The value of coefficient B is .420. So, significant and positive relationship between positive thinking and communication sub variable of job satisfaction is present. Results also explain that positive thinking is bringing 12.5 % variation in the job satisfaction of university faculty in both sectors thus rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job satisfaction.

SUMMARY, FINDING, DISCUSSION, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

The research was a comparative study of positive thinking and job satisfaction among university faculty in Islamabad. The main objective of the research was to compare the universities in both (public and private) sectors of Islamabad regarding positive thinking and job satisfaction. Further objective of the study was to find out the relationship of positive thinking and job satisfaction among the university faculty.

The present study was comparative survey and it used a quantitative research approach. There were two variable: first was positive thinking and the second was job satisfaction. For measuring the job satisfaction, the scale developed by Paul E. Spector (1994) was selected. It consisted of nine dimensions including pay, promotion, rewards, supervision, coworker, benefits, operating condition, nature of work and communication. There were 36 number of items under these nine dimensions and six-point scale was used. For measuring the positive thinking the scale developed by Carver, (2013) was used. It consisted of two dimensions which were optimism and pessimism. There were 10 number of items used under these two dimensions. Five-point scale was used to measure positive thinking of university faculty.

Another section was developed with the name of respondent demographics and it was used to collect

the data and information related to sample. Information regarding the age group, gender, teaching experience and academic qualification of faculty was asked for calculating the mean difference among the university faculty which have been working in both sectors. Statistical operations were used for the analysis of data. Mean, Standard Deviation, Regression analysis, Correlation, ANOVA and t-test were used for data analysis.

Findings

Finding regarding relationship of positive thinking and job satisfaction of university faculty in public and private sector

To find out the relationship of positive thinking and job satisfaction level of faculty members in public and private universities of Islamabad.

H0: There is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job Satisfaction level of faculty members in public and private sector universities of Islamabad.

As indicated in findings of Regression analysis that there is a positive relationship between positive thinking and job satisfaction it was 8.5% of variance, null hypothesis was not accepted that there is no association found between the positive thinking and job satisfaction. As score F=41.319, p=.000. (Table=4.6)

Regression analysis findings illustrated that there was a significant and positive relationship found between positive thinking and pay, a sub variable of job satisfaction with 5.5 % of the variance so null hypothesis was not accepted that there is no association found between the positive thinking and job satisfaction. F=25.927, p=.000. (Table=4.8)

As indicated in findings of Regression analysis that there was a significant and positive relationship between positive thinking and promotion variable of job satisfaction, it was present with 2.5% of variance, null hypothesis was not accepted that there is no association found between the positive thinking and job satisfaction. As score F=11.400, p=.001. (Table=4.9)

Regression analysis findings illustrated that there was significant and positive relationship found between positive thinking and reward sub variable of job satisfaction with 5.2 % of variance so null hypothesis was not accepted that there is no association found between the positive thinking and job satisfaction. $F=24.513, p=.000$. (Table=4.10)

As indicated in findings of Regression analysis that significant and positive relationship between positive thinking and supervision variable of job satisfaction was present with 3.7% of variance, null hypothesis was not accepted that there is no relationship found between the positive thinking and job satisfaction. As score $F=17.277, p=.000$. (Table=4.11)

Regression analysis findings described that there was significant and positive relationship found between positive thinking and coworker, a sub variable of job satisfaction with 5.9 % of variance so null hypothesis was not accepted that there is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job satisfaction. $F=27.958, p=.000$. (Table=4.12)

Regression analysis findings described that there was significant and positive relationship was found between positive thinking and benefits a sub variable of job satisfaction with 2.7 % of variance so null hypothesis was not accepted that there is no relationship found between the positive thinking and job satisfaction. $F=12.223, p=.001$. (Table=4.13)

As indicated in findings of Regression analysis that there was significant and positive relationship between positive thinking and operating condition, a variable of job satisfaction was present with 1.6 % of variance, null hypothesis was not accepted that there is no association found between the positive thinking and job satisfaction. As score $F=7.190, p=.008$. (Table=4.14)

Regression analysis findings illustrated that there was significant and positive relationship found between positive thinking and nature of work, a sub variable of job satisfaction with 5.4 % of variance so null hypothesis was not accepted that there is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job satisfaction. $F=25.220, p=.000$. (Table=4.15)

Regression analysis results described that there was significant and positive relationship found between positive thinking and communication, a sub variable of job satisfaction with 12.5 % of variance so null

hypothesis was not accept that there is no significant relationship between the positive thinking and job satisfaction. $F=63.825, p=.000$. (Table=4.16)

Discussion

Objective of study was to explore the association of positive thinking and job satisfaction of university faculty in both sectors (public and private sector universities). A significant and positive relationship was found between positive thinking and job satisfaction of faculty of university in both (public and private) sector.

Research conducted by Price. 1993; Fernandez, 1999) shows that Inadequate motivation of employees can create negative moods among workers which can affect productivity/ performance and their job satisfaction. Another Study describes that negative thinking and emotions have a negative impact on job performance and satisfaction. (McConville and Cooper, 2003).

Conclusions

The present research studied comparison of positive thinking and job satisfaction of faculty in both sectors of universities in Islamabad. 447 teachers were selected for the sample of research from public and private sector universities. Thus three objectives and hypotheses were formulated. The conclusions of this study are based on the collected data, data analysis and research results. It was concluded that difference was found regarding positive thinking and job satisfaction in both strata (public and private sector universities).

Objective of the research was concerned with the relationship of positive thinking and job satisfaction of faculty members in both (public and private) sector universities. It was concluded that there was a positive relationship between positive thinking and job satisfaction of faculty members.

It was also revealed that positive thinking have positive relationship with pay, promotion, benefit, reward, supervision, operating condition, nature of work, coworker and communication dimensions of job satisfaction.

Recommendations

Since the study draws significant conclusion, so it was important to recommend following considerations which can be used to promote positive thinking and job satisfaction among university teachers in both (public and private) sector universities:

1. Conferences, seminars and workshop may be conducted on positive psychology to enhance the positive thinking of faculty. Teachers with positive attitude may help students to develop positive attitude.
2. Training motivate employees and increase their productivity so in training sessions for development of positive thinking different techniques can be used like positive self-talk, meditation, yoga and the three-minute breathing space.
3. As the aspect of positive thinking is important. Universities may use the scale of positive thinking for measuring as well for enhancing and maintaining the positive attitude among their faculties. Positive thinking measurement may also be done on the students and administration.
4. Positive thinking and its relation with job satisfaction may be made clear for future researches. The present research may be used as a baseline and further researcher may also be done in the same areas.
5. Incentives like pay and bonuses may be provided to the competent employees to enhance the satisfaction level and this may also work as source of motivation for other employees.
6. Nature of work plays an important role for boosting the job satisfaction among employees. Universities may make teachers work meaningful for them which is not only helpful for the growth of teachers but also a source of incentive initiator in future.
7. Appreciation and recognition due to their performance may be given to employees for increasing their job satisfaction. This may also be the source for other employees to increase their performance.
8. Opportunities for enhancing the qualification may be given to employees for boosting their satisfaction level with their job.

9. Access to information regarding nature of job, polies of organization and administration may be available to employees it can motivate employees, develop a sense of belongingness with organization and it may increase the level their of job satisfaction

Trainings and workshops regarding the use of new technology and work may be organized for employees. This may update the knowledge and contribute for the job satisfaction.

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